

WHAT INFLUENCES JOB SATISFACTION IN THE NEW NORMAL? INSIGHTS FROM EDUCATORS OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY UNIT/COLLEGE IN A STATE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

This study on job satisfaction among educators in an Industrial Technology Unit/College of a State University in the new normal education setting was a descriptive research; conducted during the first quarter year 2024 among instructors and professors. This study showed that majority of the respondents are male, Master's degree holder, and teaching in the University for less than two decade as Instructor 1. This study utilized the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) of Paul E. Spector (1985) with nine facet scale to assess employee attitudes about the job satisfaction. The instructor/professor-respondents strongly agreed that the Nature of Work was strongly approved aspect/facet of job satisfaction. The respondents find enjoyment in what they are doing (teaching and other services), hence their actions and practices manifest commitment, dedication and satisfaction. The job satisfaction of the instructors/professors was also contributed by facets Supervision, Coworkers and Communication. The findings clearly shows that the social aspects of the facets of the JS survey (Spector, 1985) were more emphasized and valued by the respondents and influenced their satisfaction in their respective tasks, teaching loads and other endeavors in the university such as research, extension, production and other projects and activities.

Keywords: Instructor, Professor, Job Satisfaction, 'New Normal', Industrial Technology Unit.

INTRODUCTION

In an organization, human resource is foremost resource of the organization to work. Teachers are a valuable human resource in every society. According to Mgaiwa (2023), the landscape of the academic profession in many countries around the world has undergone a drastic change and transformation. Teachers stayed despite difficult situations during and post pandemic while others struggled. Academic profession in recent years has been pre-occupied with increased workloads (Mgaiwa, 2023); the need to utilize technology and specialized tools and equipment (Wang, 2021); and virtual conduct of teaching to address the digital divide; to keep abreast with the trends; and assure continuous education (de Guzman & Villalobos, 2023).

Employees' job satisfaction can be considered a lens on understanding job retention, burnout, commitment, and contentment to mention some. Understanding job satisfaction of teachers is far reaching as it can also affect career longevity and tenure. Financial and non-financial factors also have to be considered and analyzed in connection with job satisfaction. Aruldoss, et al. (2023) claimed that when employees are satisfied with their job, they are more committed to it than those who are not. For Astibe, et al. (2023), keeping teachers who are satisfied with their job benefits everyone.

Arante (2023) argued that organization's deteriorating working conditions has to do with the truncated job satisfaction rate Colleges may continue to pay attention to always conduct activities to further improve the performance of their employees; allow employees to contribute to decision making and problem solving too (Astibe, et al, 2023).

Colleges may create an atmosphere of commitment, cooperation due diligence and respect to policies. According to de Guzman & Villalobos (2023), the study on job satisfaction is crucial to see in a deeper spectrum the dynamics and facets of job satisfaction in the post pandemic; and to strengthen empirical evidence and knowledge on how to facilitate and nurture employee work satisfaction. If taken for granted, there will be serious social, structural, and educational consequences for the higher education system. Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction is considered as a measure of workers' contentedness with their job (Ahmadi, 2022). This study used the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) of Paul E. Spector (1985). The Job Satisfaction Survey, JSS is a 36 item, nine facet scale to assess employee attitudes about the job and aspects of the job. The nine facets are Pay, Promotion, Supervision, Fringe Benefits, Contingent Rewards (performance-based rewards), Operating Procedures (required rules and procedures), Coworkers, Nature of Work, and Communication.

The results of the present study is suitable for managers and administrators of State University and College primarily Industrial Technology Unit/Department as they can use the findings to design and present policies and procedures to further employees job satisfaction, motivation, productivity and commitment in an educational setting as a result of years of pandemic.

Objective of the Study

This study described the instructor/professor responders' job satisfaction amidst the 'new normal' educational landscape in Higher Education Institution, particularly Industrial Technology Unit/College of President Ramon Magsaysay State University (PRMSU) Iba Zambales Philippines. The study specifically answered the following questions:

1. How may the instructor/professor responders' be described in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, academic rank, number of years teaching and area of specialization?
2. How may the respondents describe their job satisfaction in terms of facets Pay, Promotion, Supervision, Fringe Benefits, Contingent Rewards, Operating Procedures, Coworkers, Nature of Work, and Communication?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study described the respondents' job satisfaction in the 'new normal' utilizing descriptive research design. Descriptive design of research is fitting for educational research, social sciences and management (see Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The forty two respondents were the instructors and professors of Industrial Technology Department of President Ramon Magsaysay State University (PRMSU), Iba, Zambales, Philippines.

The respondents' personal profile were determine in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, academic rank/administrative position, number of years teaching and area of

specialization. A standardized instrument by Paul E. Spector (1985) called Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) was utilized to assess or measure the perception of the respondents on aspects of JSS they agreed or disagreed that it can contribute to their sense of job satisfaction. The nine facets of Spector’s JSS are Pay, Promotion, Supervision, Fringe Benefits, Contingent Rewards, Operating Procedures, Coworkers, Nature of Work, and Communication in four point scale of 4-Strongly Agree; 3-Agree; 2-Disagree; and 1-Strongly Disagree. The researcher sought the approval of the University President for the administration of the survey checklist to Industrial Technology instructors and professors in all of the campuses of the University. The administration of the survey checklist was done though face-to-face in person and google form during the first quarter year 2024. The purpose and outcome of the study were discussed and the confidentiality of their responses were assured. The retrieved instrument were tabulated and analyzed using SPSS version 28.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

1. Personal Profile of the Instructor/Professor Respondents

Table 1 shows the result (frequency and percentage distribution) on the Personal Profile of the Teacher Respondents in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, academic rank/administrative position, number of years teaching and area of specialization.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Instructor/Professor Respondents’ Personal Profile

Sex	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Female	31	73.81
Male	11	26.19
Total	42	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percent
Baccalaureate with Masters Units	9	26.19
Master’s Holder	15	35.71
Masters with EdD/ PhD units	10	23.81
EdD/PhD Holder	6	14.29
Total	42	100.00
Academic Rank	Frequency	Percent
Professor	1	2.39
Associate Professor	3	7.14
Assistant Professor	9	21.43
Instructor	29	69.04
Total	42	100.00
Number of Years Teaching	Frequency	Percent
Total	42	100.00
Mean = 16.41		
Area of Specialization	Frequency	Percent
Automotive Tech	6	14.29
Drafting Tech	5	11.90

Industrial Arts	6	14.29
Food & Service Management Tech	5	11.90
Welding and Fabrication Tech	3	7.14
Computer Programming	5	11.90
Electrical Tech	3	7.14
Electronics Tech	3	7.14
Civil Tech	2	4.76
Mechanical Tech	4	9.52
Total	42	100.00

Sex: Majority of the instructor/professor-respondents in the Unit/College are male (31 or 73.81%) and the remaining 11 (26.19%) are female teachers. This result implies that the majority of the instructor/professors in the Industrial Technology Unit is represented by men.

Highest Educational Attainment: Most (15 or 35.71%) of the instructor/professor-respondents are Master’s degree holders followed by Masters with EdD/PhD units and (10 or 23.81%); Baccalaureate degree holders with Masters units (9 or 26.19%); and EdD/PhD holders (6 or 14.29%). The result suggests that the instructor/professor respondents are Master’s degree holders or have achieved the minimum educational requirement to teach in higher education or tertiary level. The Merit System for faculty members stipulated that the minimum requirement for instructor to teach in a college or university in the country is Master’s degree.

Academic Rank/Administrative Position: There are 9 (21.43) Assistant Professor; Associate Professor (3 or 7.14%); Professor (1 or 2.39%); and Instructor I (29 or 69.04%). Majority of the teaching force of the college was Instructor I (29 out of 42 or 69.04%). This result signifies that the respondents belong to the lowest academic position of Instructor 1 [National Budget Circular (NBC) Number 461, Department of Budget and Management, 1998]. Himalin & de Guzman (2020) showed that majority of the teacher respondents are Instructor 1.

Number of Years Teaching: The mean years of service was 16.41. The instructors/professors of the present study have been serving in the teaching profession for less than two decades. This condition means that the respondents are long-serving and experienced teachers in their respective area of specialization as supported by high percentage of respondents (15 or 35.71%) who are holders of master’s degree.

2. Perception on the Job Satisfaction of the Instructor/Professor Respondents

Table 2: Instructors/Professors’ Job Satisfaction in the New Normal

PAY	WM	DR	Rank
1. I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do.	3.39	Strongly Agree	2
2. Raises are too few and far between.	3.14	Agree	4
3. I am appreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.	3.40	Strongly Agree	1
4. I feel satisfied with my chances for salary increases.	3.35	Strongly Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.32	Agree	
PROMOTION	WM	DR	Rank
1. There is really a big chance for promotion on my job.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3

2. Those that do well on the job stand a fair chance of being promoted.	3.38	Strongly Agree	2
3. People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places.	3.21	Agree	4
4. I am satisfied with my chances for promotion.	3.44	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree	
SUPERVISION	WM	DR	Rank
1. My supervisor is competent in doing his/her job.	4.08	Strongly Agree	1
2. My supervisor is fair to me.	3.70	Strongly Agree	3
3. My supervisor shows interest in the feelings of subordinates.	3.74	Strongly Agree	2
4. I like my supervisor.	3.65	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.78	Strongly Agree	
FRINGE BENEFITS	WM	DR	Rank
1. I am satisfied with the benefits I receive.	3.32	Strongly Agree	2
2. The benefits we receive are as good as most other organizations offer.	3.29	Strongly Agree	3
3. The benefit package we have is equitable.	3.17	Agree	4
4. The benefits I receive is equitable	3.39	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.29	Strongly Agree	
CONTINGENT REWARDS	WM	DR	Rank
1. When I do a good job, I receive the recognition for it.	3.31	Strongly Agree	3
2. I feel that the work I do is appreciated.	3.43	Strongly Agree	1
3. There are enough rewards for those who work here.	3.25	Agree	4
4. I feel my efforts are rewarded the way they should be.	3.36	Strongly Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.34	Strongly Agree	
OPERATING PROCEDURES	WM	DR	Rank
1. Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job easy.	3.32	Strongly Agree	1
2. My efforts to do a good job are further encouraged	3.27	Strongly Agree	2
3. I have too much to do at work.	3.21	Agree	3
4. I have too much paperwork.	3.17	Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.24	Agree	
COWORKERS	WM	DR	Rank
1. I like the people I work with.	3.58	Strongly Agree	3
2. I do not work harder than I should because I work with competent people	3.38	Strongly Agree	4
3. I enjoy the company of my coworkers.	3.82	Strongly Agree	2
4. My coworkers prefer a cordial relationship at work	4.09	Strongly Agree	1
Overall Weighted Mean	3.71	Agree	
NATURE OF WORK	WM	DR	Rank
1. I feel my job is meaningful.	4.22	Strongly Agree	2
2. I like doing the things I do at work.	4.31	Strongly Agree	1
3. I feel a sense of pride in doing my job	4.19	Strongly Agree	3
4. My job is enjoyable	3.87	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	4.14	Strongly Agree	
COMMUNICATION	WM	DR	Rank
1. Communications is good within this organization.	3.63	Strongly Agree	2
2. The goals of this organization are clear to me.	3.71	Strongly Agree	1
3. I know what is going on with the organization.	3.40	Strongly Agree	3
4. Work assignments are often fully explained.	3.29	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	Strongly Agree	

Weighted Mean: WM Descriptive Rating: DR

2.1. Pay

Indicator 3 “I am appreciated by the organization when I think about what they pay me.” obtained a weighted mean of 3.40, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 2 “Raises are too few and far between” (WM=3.14) interpreted as Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Fringe Benefits as job satisfaction facet was 3.32 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The perception of the instructor/professor respondents signifies that the compensation they receive is what is due to them and the Administration pays them based on merit and performance. The salary they receive is one of the most cited reasons why employee thrives and pursues most particularly this post pandemic era.

People in all walks of life work to be able to survive, to live and to satisfy basic needs and also wants. According to Srimarut & Mekhum (2020) money provides sustenance, security, and privilege. In connection with Maslow’s (1943) Hierarchy of Needs, people need money for food, water, warmth and rest. People need money or resources to spend on truly basic needs to survive.

A fair amount of money that is earned from working (hours or days) is still a major factor to consider when it comes to their job satisfaction (de Guzman & Villalobos, 2023). The respondents of Arante (2023) revealed that their satisfaction can be attributed to the yearly increase in salary based on Salary Standardization Law implemented by the Philippine Government in four tranches.

2.2. Promotion

Indicator 4 “I am satisfied with my chances for promotion” obtained a weighted mean of 3.44, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 3 “People get ahead as fast here as they do in other places” (WM=3.21) interpreted as Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Promotion as job satisfaction facet was 3.34 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The instructor/professor respondents of the present study strongly considered that Promotion in the University is for everyone who are qualified and the chances are equal to each employee. This perception and condition consequently counts to the respondents’ feeling of satisfaction on their job. This result also suggests that one of the main reasons why the instructors/professors pursue and thrive in their respective workload and task in the new normal is promotion in their academic rank.

Link between performance, promotion and reward maintained by the existing system (Arante, 2023). Recruiting and promoting subordinates that considers personality, integrity and competence will allow for equal and equitable chances for advancement for the workforce (Fitriana, et al., 2021). Promotion also include pay raise and benefits, prestige and more responsibilities (Perugini & Vladisavljević, 2019). The financial gain of being promoted to higher academic rank impact one’s job satisfaction and enjoyment as well as needs as a human being. The aspect of promotion drives employees to have a dedication and loyalty towards an

organization (de Guzman & Villalobos, 2023). Promotion plays a big role in job satisfaction (Barman, 2022).

2.3. Supervision

Indicator 1 “My supervisor is competent in doing his/her job” obtained a weighted mean of 4.08, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 4 “I like my supervisor” (WM=3.65) interpreted as Strongly Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Supervision as job satisfaction facet was 3.78 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The instructor/professor respondents of the present study strongly agreed that competent and adept supervision and management of their Unit/College head contributes to increased job satisfaction. The respondents believed that the expertise of their heads in the new normal created by the COVID-19 pandemic will ensure that his/her directions will be followed and in a clear and specific manner. It is very clear to the respondents that their unit head is fitted as a leader and a manager; contributing factor to their perceived satisfaction in their job.

Head’s supervision approaches that can lead employees based on the needs of the moment; and adjust these approaches if necessary will probably engage employees to the workplace (Blanco & de Guzman (2023). Arante (2023) claimed that the interest that is shown by the superiors in the development and growth of their subordinates nurture job satisfaction. Aruldoss (2022) pointed out that fair, respectful and employee-center management and supervision is far more desirable for employees and for Nurhayati, et al. (2022), the more superior and suitable supervision of a school head, the higher the teacher's job satisfaction.

Above discussions provide inputs and arguments to university administrators and policy makers of aspect of supervision, management and administration that can add up to its employees job satisfaction.

2.4. Fringe Benefits

Indicator 2 “The benefits I receive is equitable” obtained a weighted mean of 3.39, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 3 “The benefit package we have is equitable” (WM=3.17) interpreted as Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Fringe Benefits as job satisfaction facet was 3.29 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. Fringe benefits in educations set-up can impact job satisfaction in many ways. For the instructor/professor respondents, it is satisfying if they receive equitable and reasonable fringe benefits such as cash allowance, educational assistance, health insurance, premiums for life insurance, transportation cost, foreign travel expense, vacation expense for instance in the whole duration of their stay in the University. For instance, Djordjevic & Radonic (2023) revealed that 68% are at least somewhat satisfied with their company’s healthcare plan.

Fringe benefits are additions to compensation that is fairly received by the employees (Artz, 2008 and La Chica, 2021). La Chica (2021) discussed that in the new normal, work environment and other practices have transformed and employees were challenged with fear and inadequate insurance safeguard. Artz (2008) argued further that a comprised number of

fringe benefits for employees is positively related to job satisfaction.

Benefit programs will need to be active to allow employee choice in terms of what they need to address, their unique circumstances and life stage requirements. Employers must ensure that their benefit plans are simple, effective, and forward-looking.

2.5. Contingent Rewards

Indicator 2 “I feel that the work I do is appreciated.” obtained a weighted mean of 3.43, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 3 “There are enough rewards for those who work here” (WM=3.25) interpreted as Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Operating Conditions as job satisfaction facet was 3.33 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The instructor/professor respondents of the present study strongly supports that Contingent Rewards, specifically appreciation and recognition of tasks done by employees are motivation and positive reinforcement that leads to job satisfaction. This result also signifies that industrial technology Unit/College and the University highly considered that employees should be given due recognition for doing their work well done; achieving their targets (e.g., performance indicators); and outcomes (students employment and commendable performance in board examination and feedback of employers). Leaders who recognize and reward individual accomplishments motivate and encourage teachers especially in this new normal to meet a higher level of standards.

The regular and fair implementation of CSC MC No. 1 s. 2001 (Revised Policies on Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence) directly motivates employees of a certain organization. This award system promotes a higher sense of self-worth (Fitriana, 2021) and increases the sense of belonging; reinforces positive behavior; and commending educators for their continuous dedication (Arante, 2022). Special awards help keep workers on the job and ultimately promote dedication, loyalty, and job satisfaction. Giving awards and monetary incentives that symbolize institution’s preferred behavior are but appropriate and noteworthy to employees (de Guzman, 2019).

2.6. Operating Procedures

Indicator 1 “Many of our rules and procedures make doing a good job easy” obtained a weighted mean of 3.32, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 4 “I have too much paperwork” (WM=3.17) interpreted as Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Operating Procedures as job satisfaction facet was 4.27 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. To enhance further the feeling of satisfaction at work and in the workplace, the instructor/professor respondents strongly agreed and believed that Unit/College and the University’s policies, procedures and practices at all situations and conditions be clear. Heads/administrators should provide specifics – who, what, where, when, how and why about the job and task. The instructor/professor respondents knew that it is important to meet the standards of the organization, hence rules and procedures should allow them to perform their respective tasks and assignment freely, efficiently and with quality. Even college head makes most of the decisions, these actions directs the team or team members to their roles and functions. Employees are more stimulated if leader supervises work closely and

provides regular guidance; and focused on completion of tasks. Dizon, et al. (2021) found the encouraging and motivating activities and lectures inspires employees to achieve their day-to-day targets and take delight in their work. Artz (2008) pointed out that productivity, and job commitment are boosted because their own institutions satisfy their needs by providing good working and operating conditions.

2.7. Coworkers

Indicator 4, “My coworkers prefer a cordial relationship at work” obtained a weighted mean of 4.09, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 2 “I do not work harder than I should because I work with competent people” (WM=3.82) also interpreted as Strongly Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Coworkers as job satisfaction facet was 4.71 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The instructor/professor respondents industrial technology Unit/College strongly agreed and highly preferred a pleasant, professional and respectful relationship at work and with their colleagues. This situation signifies that in the new normal setting, the respondents prefer to create and maintain a sense of camaraderie; and enhance work relationship, teamwork, and engagement. According to de Guzman & Vilalobos (2023), healthy relationships may motivate employees and increase morale. According to Djordjevic & Radonic (2023), happy employees are 13% more productive. It is therefore important that employees set aside irrelevant issues, they can focus on work tasks and become more productive. Joining and supporting professional learning communities to help colleagues and level up and learn together (Blanco & de Guzman, 2023). Collaboration and interaction with other educators as regard to instruction, research and extension activities and other projects positively leads to job satisfaction. In the new normal set-up in the industrial technology Unit/College, sharing of instructional pedagogies, knowledge, tools, materials and equipment with colleagues will arouse instructors/professors’ motivation and interest to further improve the delivery of quality service to clients-students. Spector (2022) and de Guzman & Villalobos (2023) argued that leaders need to make deliberate efforts to encourage positive social interaction amongst teams. Arante (2022) claimed that social, organizational, and physical factors are the impetus for tasks and activity, consequently impacting workers' performance.

2.10. Nature of Work

Indicator 2, “I like doing the things I do at work” obtained a weighted mean of 4.31, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 4 “My job is enjoyable” (WM=4.87) also interpreted as Strongly Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Nature of Work as job satisfaction facet was 4.14 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. The industrial technology instructor/professor respondents strongly agreed that they enjoy and find satisfaction on the task and assignments they are doing in their Unit/College. This could also mean that they find sense of pride, sense of identify and feeling of high self-esteem in their work related experiences. Calimlim, et al. (2022) revealed that the new normal in Philippine education system necessitates the utilization of different but appropriate modalities in teaching and learning (limited face-to-face, online blended, etc.) For continuous service and teaching, de Guzman & Villalobos (2023) found that lecturer-respondents strongly

agreed that the sense of comfort and pride in work is tantamount to sense of job satisfaction. With these abovementioned arguments and discussions, administrators of the industrial technology Unit/College and the University need to prioritize differentiated instructions; utilization of technology and learning management system; and the conduct varied mode of instructional deliveries (synchronous and asynchronous). Vital to satisfaction in instructional planning, procedure and execution among industrial technology instructors and professors is the continuous support from the management (deans, head of instructions and curriculum planners). Wang, et al. (2021) contend that fundamental and meaningful job of teaching in this new normal is creating knowledge that benefits both the students and society.

2.11. Communication

Indicator 2, “The goals of this organization are clear to me” obtained a weighted mean of 3.71, ranked 1st with descriptive interpretation of Strongly Agree. Least in the rank was Indicator 1 “Communications is good within this organization” (WM=63) also interpreted as Strongly Agree. The overall weighted mean (OWM) of Communication as job satisfaction facet was 3.51 with qualitative rating of Strongly Agree. Communication is a vital component to an organization, hence a comprehensive, efficient and effective communication strategies and channels should be institutionalized and maintained. Understanding how college and university vision, mission, goals and objectives in the new normal set-up in higher education affects employees and how it build stronger job commitment and fulfilment is a requirement of good governance and effective management. The instructor/professor respondents strongly agreed that they can focus on their daily task and in achieving their short and long term goals if the college and university’s targets are clear, well disseminated and understood. Open lines of communication between the instructors/professors of industrial technology department, dean and other administrators keep professional objectives clear and project focused. Arante (2023) pointed out that dissemination of information about what is going on will people in the organization be more directed and engaged. For Milano (2023) and de Guzman (2019), the ability to command dignity and respect from the job, adds up to employees satisfaction of their job.

Summary

Table 3: Summary on the Instructors/Professors’ Job Satisfaction in the New Normal

Facets of Job Satisfaction	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Rating	Rank
1. Pay	3.32	Strongly Agree	7
2. Promotion	3.34	Strongly Agree	5
3. Supervision	3.78	Strongly Agree	2
4. Fringe Benefits	3.29	Strongly Agree	8
5. Contingent Rewards	3.34	Strongly Agree	6
6. Operating Procedures	3.24	Agree	9
7. Coworkers	3.71	Strongly Agree	3
8. Nature of Work	4.14	Strongly Agree	1
9. Communication	3.51	Strongly Agree	4
Grand Mean	3.51	Strongly Agree	

Table 3 presents the summary of the instructors/professors' job satisfaction in the new normal. Nature of Work obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.14 (ranked 1st) with descriptive rating of Strongly Agree; Supervision was ranked 2nd with an overall weighted mean of 3.78 with descriptive rating of Strongly Agree; Coworkers obtained an overall weighted mean of 3.71 (ranked 3rd) interpreted as Strongly Agree; and Communication with overall weighted mean of 3.51 (ranked 4th) also interpreted as Strongly Agree. The grand mean was 3.51 with descriptive rating of Strongly Agree. The instructors/professors respondents strongly approved and believed that the Nature of Work contributed significantly to increased job satisfaction of the faculty workforce of the Industrial Technology Unit/College.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study of job satisfaction among educators in an Industrial Technology Unit/College of a University found that majority of the instructor/professor-respondents are male, Master's degree holder, and teaching in the University for less than two decade as Instructor 1.

Utilizing the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) of Paul E. Spector (1985) with nine facet scale to assess employee attitudes about the job satisfaction it was found that instructor/professor-respondents of the present study strongly agreed that the Nature of Work was strongly approved aspect of job satisfaction. The respondents find enjoyment in what they are doing (teaching and other services), hence their actions and practices manifest commitment, dedication and satisfaction. The job satisfaction of the instructors/professors was also contributed by facets of Supervision, Coworkers and Communication. Overall, the instructors/professors perceived strongly agreed that they are satisfied with their job/work at the Unit/College during the new normal. The findings clearly show that the social aspects of the facets of the JS survey (Spector, 1985) were more emphasized and valued by the instructor/professor-respondents. These mentioned facets influenced their satisfaction in their respective tasks, teaching loads and other endeavors in the unit/college and university such as research, extension and production projects and activities.

This study recommended that the University Administration and the Unit/College management have to prioritize and preserve desirable human relation; acceptable working condition; preferred organizational culture; and varied and two-way communications to preserve, nurture and maximize high level of job satisfaction among the instructors/professors.

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